

A Proof-of-Concept Study Evaluating the Impact of Comic Literacy on Meaning-Making of Microscopy Data in Microbial Systems and the Capability of LLMs as Collaborators

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ABSTRACT

This proof-of-concept study investigates the impact of a comic literacy framework on scientific narrative synthesis, a key component of a larger meaning-making framework for inclusive smart microscopy that I proposed in Güleç (2026). Using NotebookLM (Gemini 3 Flash), I evaluated how multimodal narrative logic (comic literacy logic) influences a Large Language Model's (LLM) ability to interpret microscopy data from microbial biofilms and spores. I used an LLM-as-a-Judge approach with Chain-of-Thought prompting to compare three narratives (baseline, framework-guided, and context-enhanced) against ground-truth papers. Results indicate that the comic literacy framework enhances the "Narrative Leap," enabling the artificial intelligence (AI) to transition from simple data description to high-level scientific insight and relational reasoning. This work provides a foundation for developing AI as a meaning-making collaborator.

INTRODUCTION

In my previous work (Güleç, 2026), I established lack of narrative synthesis as one of the main challenges towards a meaning-making smart microscopy, aligning with Kesavan and Nordenfelt (2025). This is not unique to smart microscopy but also true for other scientific applications employing AI-based systems. Despite the increasing popularity of Large Language Models (LLM) in scientific research, most LLM applications still focus on generating literature reviews and replies, or are limited to domain-specific applications such as discovering new proteins, chemicals, rather than using them as meaning-making, insight-providing collaborators (Tang et al., 2023; Zhang, Y. et al., 2025). To close the gap towards the meaning-making AI collaborator, I proposed a meaning-making framework (Figure 1) based on multimodal narrative design, literacy, and cross-modal synthesis for smart microscopy in Güleç (2026). From this point on, I will refer to multimodal narrative as comic. Comic design and literacy are foundational for the implementation of meaning-making in LLMs, especially for smart microscopy, as they can handle non-linearity, simultaneity, and promote relational thinking while moving from panel to panel in the gutters (the gap between the panels) and advantage of microscopic data resembling comic panels. Here, I present a proof-of-concept study focusing on the comic literacy part of the whole framework proposed in Güleç (2026). More specifically, I tested the impact of the comic literacy logic on creating scientific narrative synthesis of selected microscopy datasets using LLM for both generating and evaluating the narratives. To my knowledge, this is the first time a comic-literacy-based meaning-making framework was used for scientific data and narrative synthesis.

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METHODOLOGY

Narrative Generation

Given its capabilities in narrative generation, computer vision, and multimodal processing, I used a Large Language Model (LLM) to generate scientific narratives. Specifically, I used NotebookLM (NLM), powered by Gemini 3 Flash. NLM employs Retrieval-Augmented-Generation (RAG), which ensures that the generated narratives are grounded in the sources provided, hence reducing the likelihood of hallucinations.

I employed a zero-shot approach guided by cross-domain structural context. This involves generating the scientific narratives on the first attempt upon prompting, without

providing prior examples of completed dataset-to-narrative syntheses. However, to guide the scientific narrative synthesis, the model uses the comic story and reference logic files as structural maps.

To evaluate the impact of comic literacy, I employed an ablation method (see prompts in Appendix A). In this approach, at each step, I uploaded a new source to the NLM as follows:

Narrative 0: the baseline narrative, generated using only the dataset.

Narrative 1: included the dataset, reference logic file, and comic story.

Narrative 2: included the dataset, reference logic file, comic story, and one background paper.

To provide the best historical context for each topic, I selected background papers from the references used in the original studies. Table 1 lists the background papers chosen for each topic.

I generated each narrative across three independent runs using identical prompts. All generated narratives are available in Supplementary Information 3.

Datasets

I used microscopy images and, in some cases, also included measurements based on microscopy images in selected studies as my dataset. Table 1 shows datasets, the ground truth papers where the datasets originated, and background papers. Data descriptions are already present in the generated narratives (Supplementary Information 3).

I chose the datasets based on image quality, spatiotemporal, and zoomed-in-out features. To minimize data leakage in NLM, I did minor modifications such as relabeling or stacking zoomed-in images on top of each other (which is like overlaid panels in comics).

Meaning-making Framework: Comic Literacy Part

As a reference comic (Supplementary Information 2), I selected one of my own comics titled “A Pedogenetic Resolution of Spacetime Paradox.” From the title to the entire story, it effectively illustrates the power of comics in handling nonlinearity, simultaneity, and spatiotemporal relationships. Although the topic includes microbial processes as part of soil formation, it creates enough distance to prevent the NLM from mimicking the comic’s story. However, it is also scientific and complex enough to introduce and demonstrate comic literacy, enabling the creation of scientific narrative synthesis from microbiology datasets. Moreover, the comic story incorporates philosophical, emotional, and mythological elements, adding depth and complexity to the narrative. This, I think, contributes to better reasoning and narrative leaps while the scientific part keeps the NLM grounded. When combined with strict prompts and scientific references, this framework transforms into a powerful tool for meaning-making of microbiology data.

The “Reference Logic” file (Supplementary Information 1) provides detailed descriptions of each panel layout, conveying the story, the intended intentions, and rationales behind each panel and page to illustrate the meaning-making process.

Table 1.Datasets, ground truth and background papers per topic

Topic	Dataset (as presented in the ground truth paper)	Ground Truth Paper (Where the dataset originated)	Background Paper
Membrane Potential	Figure 1.c	Prindle et al. (2015)	Liu et al. (2015)
Spatiotemporal Colony Growth	Figure 1.a-c Figure 7.g-j Figure S2. a-h	Kannan et al. (2025)	Warren et al. (2019)
Biofilm Formation	Figure 6.a	Marra et al. (2025)	Benoit and Klaus (2007)
Biofilm Matrix	Figure 1.a-c. (schematic above the image in a is removed) Figure2.a-b Figure5.a-b. (only first column of “a” is used)	Heredia-Ponce et al. (2026)	Ghafoor et al. (2011)
Spore Germination 1	Figure 2.d (mutant line is removed) Figure 2.e	Kikuchi et al. (2022)	Brunel and van Rossum (2007)
Spore Germination 2	Figure 2.d (mutant line is removed) Figure 2.e		Pandey et al. (2013)
Spore Germination 3	Figure 2.d-f Figure 4.c-d		Pandey et al. (2013)

Narrative Evaluation

Recent studies have shown that LLMs are becoming increasingly promising in narrative evaluations. Chhun et al. (2024) found that LLMs outperform automatic evaluation metrics like BLEU and ROUGE. Zheng et al. (2023) proposed a LLM-as-a-Judge approach that achieved strong agreement with human experts. As for scientific narratives, Evans et al. (2024) highlighted the potential of LLMs in scientific synthesis evaluations, and some researchers like Wysocka et al. (2024) and Zhang, H. et al. (2025) have already obtained promising results by using LLMs with that purpose. Hence, to evaluate the narratives in this study, I used an LLM-as-a-Judge approach, comparing the narratives to the ground truth papers (Table 1) where the dataset originated.

I used a Two-Stage Zero-Shot Evaluation approach:

- Stage 1 (Objective-Based Evaluation): I initially prompted the model to generate an evaluation rubric based on my objectives, without providing prior grading examples.
- Stage 2 (Reference-Based Refinement): I then uploaded specific reference papers on systematic evaluation and selected metrics to focus on, prompting the model to refine its generated rubric against those standards.

In both stages, I used Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting, requiring the NLM to generate intermediate reasoning steps (including fact-checking verifications, definitions, rationales) prior to outputting the final evaluation scores. [see Appendix B]. I used Gemini 3.0 to refine and polish prompts to maximize prompt effectiveness and clarity.

For objective-based evaluations, I defined the objectives as follows:

1. **The Narrative Leap:** The ability to bridge raw data observations into high-level scientific conclusions and insights, relational power.
2. **Data Integrity, Logical Flow, Reasoning:** Identifying missing critical variables and logical flow, coherence.
3. **Data Efficiency:** quantity of data compared to the quantity in the original paper to reach the same conclusions and insights.

For the reference-based refinements, after selecting the candidate metrics from literature, I filtered and reduced them into 5 evaluation metrics aligned with the study's specific objectives using NLM. Instead of using rigid, predefined templates, at each evaluation, I prompted the NLM to state the definitions and rationales together with the examples for each metric by extracting the information from the reference papers Yi et al. (2025), Wysocka et al. (2024), and Zhang, H. et al. (2025). (See evaluation prompts in Appendix B.) Table 2 shows an example NLM output of metric definitions to provide an overview for the reader. Outputs for all evaluations are accessible in Supplementary Information 4.

Table 2. Narrative evaluation metrics as defined by the NLM

Metric	Metric as in Reference Papers	Definitions
Accuracy	Factuality & Soundness	Factuality is defined as alignment with factual statements in trusted scientific literature. Soundness evaluates the rigor of empirical substantiation.
Semantic Similarity	Coherence & Consistency	Coherence measures average logical flow and "semantic flow" across responses. Consistency tracks the fraction of responses that do not conflict with previously stated info.
Semantic Gap	Item Status & State Tracking	"Item Status" tracks the percentage of required items (entities/variables) present. "Dynamic State Tracking" monitors the transition of items through states to catch logic errors.
Scientific Insight	Complex QA + Info Gain	"Complex QA" is the ability to answer multi-hop reasoning questions. "Scientific Insight" involves synthesizing knowledge to create new actionable insights beyond raw data.
Data Efficiency	(Introduced by the author at Stage 1 objective based evaluations)	The ability to yield "paper-level" insights using only a subset of data compared to the Ground Truth paper

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Narrative evaluations revealed a hierarchical performance of the narrative categories (N0, N1, and N2) regardless of the microbiological topics, both for reference-based refinements (Figure 2) and objective-based evaluations (shown as “core metrics” in Supplementary Information 4). N0 baseline narratives are mainly descriptive, treating snapshots as isolated data points and often failing to bridge the gaps between observations and mechanisms. N1 narratives, generated by providing the meaning-making framework alongside the data sets, exhibit better logical flow and depth compared to baseline narratives. N1 narratives can identify transitions and transformations, effectively bridging the gaps between observations and general mechanisms, although they may occasionally miss specific mechanisms. N2 narratives, generated by providing one background paper in addition to the meaning-making framework and datasets, demonstrate the highest level of synthesis, reaching the same level of conclusions and insights as the original papers using only limited datasets. This hierarchical performance aligns with the pyramid proposed by Zhang H. et al. (2025), categorizing N0 as evaluator, N1 as collaborator, and N2 as scientist. The meaning-making framework significantly benefits N1 and N2 narratives by tracking status and state transitions (reducing semantic gaps), gaining insights from limited datasets (enhancing data efficiency and information gain), and bridging gaps between observations and mechanisms (enhancing relational power and information gain). Examples of each topic, as summarized by NLM, are presented in Table 3a and 3b. Full narratives and evaluations are accessible in the Supplementary Information 3 and 4.

As shown in Figure 2, some baseline narratives achieved high scores, which can be attributed to the characteristics of the dataset, allowing more descriptive and informative narratives. Additionally, some topics are more prevalent and well-known, making data interpretation and mechanistic explanation easier. As Figure 2 shows, the difference between N0 and N1, and N1 and N2, is more pronounced for some topics, such as biofilm membrane potential. On the other hand, for the biofilm matrix study, the baseline, N0, scored higher and much closer to N1 and N2. The biofilm matrix study is predominantly focused on microbiology and molecular biology, and most of the topics covered have been extensively discussed in literature for a longer period compared to biophysics studies, like membrane potential in biofilms. Although NLM is constrained to disregard the original study and knowledge published after the publication year during narrative generation, and it heavily relies on the provided sources, it can still reflect its training on the synthesis given the topic’s widespread nature. Indeed, it was already acknowledged by Wysocka et al. (2024) that higher prevalence of scientific literature leads to better fact knowledge extraction.

Moreover, the quantity of data and the background paper significantly impact the evaluation. This is evident in the spore germination case, as illustrated in Figure 2. When the quantity of data is lower and the background paper is from neuroscience, the insights for N0, N1, and N2 exhibit a large difference. However, when more data is provided and the background paper is about spore germination, the difference between metric scores is smaller, although N2 remains the best performer.

While applied here to microscopy, this meaning-making framework successfully circumvents the limitations of LLMs in comic-specific applications, such as LLMs’ struggles with non-linear narratives, consistency, and reasoning when processing Manga (comics) (Baranwal et al.,2025), or additional post-training strategies such as Region-

Aware Reinforcement Learning (Chen et al., 2025) or multistep pipelines composed of detection, identification, captioning, and prose generation (Sachdeva and Zisserman, 2025) to improve narrative reasoning. Indeed, my framework performed well to create narrative synthesis of my other comic stories as well (data not shown).

LIMITATIONS

- Sample size is limited; evaluating more data sets would provide a more robust validation of the framework's impact.
- As this was a proof-of-concept study, I only used NLM, which is a RAG-based system. In the future, testing the framework with different foundational LLMs would be valuable.
- Here I used zero-shot prompting guided by cross-domain structural context, but in the future, fine-tuning the models to incorporate the meaning-making framework would benefit the performance in narrative synthesis as well as testing the impact of the framework.
- How prompts are engineered affects the outcome, from the choice of words to the order of instructions. Chhun et al. (2024) noted that detailed prompts did not significantly alter the evaluations. Based on my experience, detailed prompts and ground truth reference result in quite good performance with the NLM. Indeed, the SCORE framework by Yi et al. (2025) mitigated Chhun's limitations and demonstrated that detailed prompts indeed improved the performance of LLMs.
- This study only employed NLM-generated synthesis and evaluations. Including human-generated synthesis and human-based evaluations would enhance the assessment of the impact of the meaning-making framework.
- Narratives are evaluated against the ground truth papers. However, NLM can be too strict; it may over-penalize the narratives for omitting certain insights found in the original study even if those insights can't be generated by the limited dataset used in narrative synthesis.
- The data sets are taken from published studies, which has the advantage of comparing the narratives to the ground truth papers. While the prompts are constrained to prevent data leakage, unpublished data would eliminate the risk of pre-training contamination. Although how widespread the topic also affects the synthesis, as discussed before.

Figure 2. Narrative Evaluation Scores. A) Membrane Potential B) Spatiotemporal Colony Growth C) Biofilm Matrix D) Biofilm Formation E) Spore Germination-1 F) Spore Germination-2 G) Spore Germination-3. N0: Narrative 0 (Baseline) N1: Narrative 1 N2: Narrative 2. Color gradient is used to differentiate regions: N0 (inner) is shown with high color intensity, transitioning through N1 (middle) to N2 (outer) at low color intensity.

Table 3a. Examples from NLM for the impact of meaning-making framework

Topic	Narrative 0 (Dataset)	Narrative 1 (Dataset + Framework)	Narrative 2 (Dataset+Framework+ Background Paper)
Biofilm Membrane Potential	Views fluorescent time-series as isolated snapshots, failing to track the status of metabolic states across the colony's radius.	Views the biofilm as an "integrated electrical unit" and identifies the hyperpolarization wave as a relay for resource allocation.	Deduces the "metabolic co-dependence" model. It identifies the "Interior Trigger" (glutamate deprivation in the core) as the specific driver for the peripheral electrical wave
Spatiotemporal Colony Growth	Remains primarily descriptive, treating time points as isolated snapshots. It suffers from hallucinations, incorrectly concluding that glucose concentration drives radial expansion speed	Improves by tracking metabolic states (necrotic core vs. viable shell) and viewing growth as a "continuous process". However, it lacks the "Narrative Leap" to identify mechanical constraints.	Correctly identifies the "Buckling Transition"—a high-level insight that radial expansion is a mechanical constant governed by cell verticalization, not nutrient concentration.
Biofilm Formation	Struggles to integrate the role of gravity, incorrectly assuming high flow "nullifies" its effects.	Characterizes the data as a "sequential transformation" from 2D surface presence to 3D community building. It remains more efficient than N0 but still misses persistent biovolume asymmetry.	Frames the data as transitions between physical regimes (e.g., "diffusion-limited" to "convection-dominated"). It successfully infers that initial sedimentation dictates final architecture, even under high shear.
Biofilm Matrix	Suffers a significant accuracy failure by incorrectly claiming the cellulose matrix is a "shared resource" that stabilizes non-producers.	Maintains a logical progression from "stochastic attachment" to "emerging frameworks" but may still repeat accuracy errors regarding matrix sharing	Frames the spatial gradient as a "spatial continuum" representing the biofilm's past and future maturity. It correctly identifies cellulose as a "private good" and "communal gatekeeper"

Table 3b. Examples from NLM for the impact of meaning-making framework continues from Table 3a.

Topic	Narrative 0 (Dataset)	Narrative 1 (Dataset + Framework)	Narrative 2 (Dataset+Framework+ Background Paper)
Spore Germination 1	Primarily descriptive and prone to significant accuracy failures. A notable "major hallucination" occurs in replicate N0.2, which incorrectly claims Pulse 1 triggers ~55% germination, whereas the ground truth is only ~5%.	Employs the framework to view intervals between pulses as a "Transformation Phase" where internal modifications lower activation thresholds. However, it remains grounded in morphological "snapshots" rather than the underlying physics.	Reaches the "Narrative Leap" by independently rediscovering the "Integrate-and-Fire" model and the "biological capacitor" analogy used in the original research. It perfectly matches the ground truth's Discussion section, explaining the "dormant" state as one that actively integrates sub-threshold inputs.
Spore Germination 2	Effectively describes the step-wise decay and identifies the concept of "memory," but remains focused on the literal drops in the graph rather than broader physiological implications.	Shows a significant improvement in logical flow by categorizing data into distinct scientific phases: Priming, Transformation, and Exhaustion. It bridges visual and quantitative data streams more seamlessly than N0.	Reaches the "Data Efficiency peak" by characterizing spores as "intermittent signal processors". It provides sophisticated evolutionary insights, identifying that the sequential transition strategy is a method for managing the risk of premature reactivation in unstable environments.
Spore Germination 3	Acts as a "Reliable Core" with high data integrity for explicit knowledge extraction. It accurately identifies the hypersensitivity of the $\Delta ktrC$ mutant but suffers from a "Semantic Gap" by failing to holistically connect this genetic importer to the internal "Integrate-and-Fire" logic.	Achieves "Analytical Depth" by framing the dormant state as a period of "progressive physiological maturation". It successfully bridges the gap between macroscopic population kinetics (the "staircase" decay) and microscopic single-cell "memory".	Demonstrates "Superhuman Synthesis," matching the high-level reasoning of the original <i>Science</i> article with minimal data. It reconstructs the "Biological Capacitor" analogy and deduces that a spore's "individual history" determines the timing of its return to life.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Following files can be accessed in Supplementary Information:

1. Reference logic
2. Pedogenesis Comic
3. NotebookLM Generated Narratives
4. NotebookLM Narrative Evaluations

APPENDIX A: Prompt Engineering Protocol for Narrative Synthesis

Prompt 1

[Context: Upload the data file]

Role & Persona:

Act as a strict scientific data analyst. Your task is to analyze the data provided in [title of the data file] objectively.

Strict Constraints:

- **No Source Leakage:** Even if you recognize the published study this dataset originates from, you must absolutely ignore that study, its conclusions, and its specific text. Treat the dataset as unpublished, raw data that you are seeing for the first time.
- **Temporal Cutoff:** Do not use any external knowledge or scientific context published after **[publication year of the original study where the dataset is originated]**

Task:

Describe the data in **[title of the data file]** and create a scientific narrative synthesis. Write this synthesis as if you are describing your data, analysis, and possible explanations directly to another scientist.

Prompt 2

[Context: Upload the pedogenesis comic and the reference logic file]

Role & Persona:

I am conducting a study to evaluate how the meaning making logic in comics can be used to create narrative synthesis to make meaning of scientific data in microbiology.

You are provided with a comic and a reference logic file containing an exemplar synthesis, panel descriptions, and a rationale for meaning-making. This serves as your "Gold Standard Dataset" for *methodology only*.

Strict Constraints:

- **No Source Leakage:** Even if you recognize the published study this dataset originates from, you must absolutely ignore that study, its conclusions, and its specific text. Treat the dataset as unpublished, raw data that you are seeing for the first time.
- **Temporal Cutoff:** Do not use any external knowledge or scientific context published after **[publication year of the original study where the dataset is originated]**
- **Strict Content Separation:** The scientific data document is entirely unrelated to the comic or reference logic used in the framework. Do *not* compare **[title of the data file]** with the comic or reference logic.
- **Vocabulary Bans:** Do *not* use specific terminologies or topics from the reference logic/comic in your final synthesis. Specifically, do *not* use words like "gutters".
- **Tone:** Use clear, accessible academic language. Avoid literary, creative, or metaphorical words.

Task:

Describe the data in **[title of the data file]** and apply the meaning-making rationale from the reference logic file to create a scientific narrative synthesis. Write this synthesis as if you are describing your data, analysis, and possible explanations directly to another scientist.

Prompt 3

[Context: Upload the background paper]

Role & Persona:

Act as a strict scientific data analyst. You are now provided with a background paper:
[Background Paper Title]

Strict Constraints:

- **No Source Leakage:** Even if you recognize the published study this dataset originates from, you must absolutely ignore that study, its conclusions, and its specific text. Treat the dataset as unpublished, raw data that you are seeing for the first time.
- **Temporal Cutoff:** Do not use any external knowledge or scientific context published after **[publication year of the original study where the dataset is originated]**
- **Information Weighting:** The background paper is an earlier study provided *only* to give historical context and support your reasoning. Do not give disproportionate weight to its specific terminology or content; use it strictly to substantiate and fuel the meaning-making framework.
- **Strict Content Separation:** The scientific data document is entirely unrelated to the comic or reference logic used in the framework. Do *not* compare **[title of the data file]** with the comic or reference logic.
- **Vocabulary Bans:** Do *not* use specific terminologies or topics from the reference logic/comic in your final synthesis. Do *not* use words like "gutters".
- **Tone:** Use clear, accessible academic language. Avoid literary words.

Task:

Describe the data in **[title of the data file]** and combine the meaning-making rationale from the reference logic file with the scientific context of the background paper to create a scientific narrative synthesis. Write this synthesis as if you are describing your data, analysis, and possible explanations directly to another scientist.

APPENDIX B: Prompt Engineering Protocol for Narrative Evaluation

Prompt 1

[Context: Upload dataset, ground truth paper and generated narratives]

Task: Evaluate the attached narratives (N0, N1, N2) by comparing them to the ground truth **[title of ground truth paper]**

Note that there 3 replicates for each narrative, for example N0.1, N0.2, N0.3 for N0 category. You will output the average score of the 3 replicates for each category.

Primary Objectives:

In this evaluation, I am specifically looking for:

1. **The Narrative Leap:** The ability to bridge raw data observations into high-level scientific conclusions and insights, relational power
2. **Data Integrity, Logical Flow, Reasoning:** Identifying missing critical variables and logical flow, coherence
3. **Data Efficiency:** number of data compared to data in the original paper to reach the same conclusions and insights

Step 1 Execution:

Before scoring, create an internal alignment mapping. Build a quick table listing key instances where the individual replicates (N0.1, N0.2, N0.3...) narratives align or deviate from the Ground Truth using direct quotes.

Step 2 Execution:

Create a custom 1-to-5 rubric based on the objectives above. Evaluate the narratives and output the results in a clean table showing the averaged scores for N0, N1, and N2. *Ensure the scoring logic prioritizes narrative reasoning depth, not the length of text.*

Prompt 2

[Context: Upload the metric papers: Yi et al (2025), Wysocka et al (2024), Zhang et al (2025)]

Task: Refine and systemize the evaluation from the previous prompt by directly mapping your findings to the specific methodologies of the uploaded papers.

Metrics:

Accuracy: Factuality & Soundness (Wysocka et al, 2024)

Semantic Similarity: Coherence & Consistency (Yi et al, 2025)

Semantic Gap: Item Status / State Tracking (Yi et al, 2025)

Scientific Insight: Complex QA (Yi et al, 2025) + Info Gain (Zhang et al, 2025)

Data Efficiency: The narrative's ability to yield paper-level insights from a subset of data compared to the full ground truth paper.

Execution:

- 1. For each metric, first provide a brief rationale explaining your evaluations based strictly on these paper definitions and examples from the narratives.**
- 2. Based strictly on the rationale you just established, determine the adjusted 1-to-5 scores for each individual replicate**
- 3. Compile these results into a final summary table showing the averaged replicate scores (N0, N1, N2).**

Ensure your internal scoring logic prioritizes narrative reasoning depth, not the length of text.